

THE EFFECT OF LIGHT INTENSITY AND TEMPERATURE ON THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF MICROALGAE

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Abstract. In this work, the effect of light intensity and temperature on the formation of the largest biomass in local strains of microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* 4, *Scenedesmus quadricauda*, *Anabaena variabilis* 17, *Nostoc linckia* 44, *Spirulina platensis* was studied. It was found that the studied strains of cyanobacteria *Nostoc linckia* 44, *Anabaena variabilis* 17 and *Spirulina platensis* form the largest amount of dry biomass at an illumination level of 2500 lux. When growing strains of unicellular green algae *C. vulgaris* 4 and *S. quadricauda* at 30 °C, the rate of biomass accumulation was higher than at 24 °C and 36 °C.

Keywords: microalgae, cyanobacteria, *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, biomass, light intensity, temperature.

Introduction

Microalgae are photosynthetic, eukaryotic, unicellular green algae belonging to the class *Chlorophyceae*, which include the genera *Haematococcus*, *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, and *Dunaliella*, most commonly used for industrial applications. In addition, diatoms and cyanobacteria are valuable biotechnological objects [1, 2]. Microalgae biomass is a sustainable bioresource for various areas such as food, natural bio-additives, pharmaceuticals, feed and other bio-products. In recent years, its mass production has attracted wide attention and interest. The production process of microalgae biomass involves several methods, mainly cultivation, harvesting, drying and pollution control. These methods often need to be developed and optimized to provide optimal growth conditions for microalgae and to produce high-quality biomass at low cost. It should be noted that mass production methods are essential for the production of sufficient quantities of commercial product [3,4]. Currently, with the development of biotechnology, global biomass production from microalgae is approaching 20,000 metric tons [5-9]. Light intensity on microalgae biomass; temperature; the composition of the nutrient medium (concentrations of nitrogen, phosphorus and other elements) and aeration are the main influencing factors [10,11]. In particular, microalgae use light as an energy source to synthesize protoplasm. The rate of cell growth is greater when it is saturated with light of maximum intensity and decreases when it is less. Temperature affects algal growth rate, cell size, biochemical composition, and nutrient uptake. Cultivation at optimal temperature ensures minimum cell size, efficient assimilation of carbon and nitrogen, and also reduces the risk of photoinhibition. If the microalgae culture temperature differs from the optimal temperature, a significant decrease in the growth rate is observed [12].

The purpose of this work is to determine the effect of light intensity and temperature on the growth and development of unicellular algae *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus* and local strains of cyanobacteria belonging to the genera *Nostoc*, *Anabaena* and *Spirulina*.

Materials and methods

Research objects: Local strains of microalgae such as *Chlorella vulgaris* 4, *Scenedesmus quadricauda*, *Anabaena variabilis* 17, *Nostoc linckia* 44, *Spirulina platensis* were used in the studies [13-15].

Nutrient media for growing microalgae: cultures belonging to the genera *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus* were grown in "Chu-13" nutrient medium, g/l: $\text{KNO}_3 - 0.2$, $\text{K}_2\text{HPO}_4 - 0.04$, $\text{MgSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.1$, $\text{CaCl}_2 \times 6\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.08$, iron citrate - 0.01, citric acid - 0.1. Microelements, $\mu\text{g/l}$: B - 0.5, $\text{MnSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.5$, $\text{CuSO}_4 \times 5\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.02$, $\text{CoCl}_2 \times 2\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.02$, $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \times 2\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.02$, growing pH -7.5. Cyanobacteria belonging to the genus *Nostoc*, *Anabaena* were grown in "M" mineral nutrient medium, (g/l): $\text{MgSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.25$; $\text{CaCl}_2 \times 2\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.25$; Na citric acid - 0.16; $\text{K}_2\text{HPO}_4 - 0.4$; $\text{KNO}_3 - 1$; trace elements, 1ml/l: $\text{FeCl}_3 \times 6\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.002$; $\text{ZnSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.222$; $\text{CuSO}_4 \times 5\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.079$; $\text{MnCl}_2 \times 4\text{H}_2\text{O} - 1.81$; $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \times 2\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.03$; $\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 - 2.80$ [16]. *Spirulina* cultures were grown in "Zarruka" medium, g/l: $\text{NaHCO}_3 - 16.8$, $\text{K}_2\text{HPO}_4 \times 3\text{H}_2\text{O} - 1.0$, $\text{NaNO}_3 - 2.5$, $\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 - 1.0$, $\text{NaCl} - 1.0$, $\text{MgSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.2$, $\text{CaCl}_2 \times 2\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.04$, Fe+EDTA - 1 ml; №1 trace elements, g/l: $\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3 - 2.86$, $\text{MnCl}_2 \times 4\text{H}_2\text{O} - 1.81$, $\text{ZnSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.22$, $\text{CuSO}_4 \times 5\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.08$, $\text{MoO}_3 - 0.015$; №2 trace elements, g/l: $\text{NH}_4\text{VO}_3 - 0.023$, $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_4 \times 24\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.096$, $\text{NiSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.048$, $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \times 2\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.018$, $\text{Ti}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 - 0.040$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \times 6\text{H}_2\text{O} - 0.044$ [17,18].

Optimization of growing conditions

To optimize the growth and development of microalgae in these nutrient media, cultures were grown for 10 days at different light intensities (1000, 2000, 2500, 3000, 4000 lux) and temperatures (24°C, 28°C, 30°C, 32°C, 36°C). Under these growth conditions, the formation of biomass of microalgae was determined.

Determination of dry weight of microalgae biomass

Dry weight of cell biomass was determined according to the following method. Biomass in glass containers was placed in a drying closet and dried at 110 °C for 2 h. The vials were then removed from the drying closet using tweezers and transferred to desiccators containing anhydrous CaCl_2 . After 1 hour, the bottles were weighed to the nearest 0.1 mg. Drying and weighing were repeated, following the established sequence of operations, until the biomass reached a constant value, that is, until the fluctuations in its determination exceeded ± 0.1 mg [19].

Results and discussion

Figure 1. A microscopic view of the cells of local strains of microalgae: 1) *Chlorella vulgaris* 4, 2) *Scenedesmus quadricauda*, 3) *Nostoc linckia* 44, 4) *Anabaena variabilis* 17, 5) *Spirulina platensis* (Magnification: 100x13,5)

In our previous studies, local strains of microalgae such as *Chlorella vulgaris* 4, *Scenedesmus quadricauda*, *Anabaena variabilis* 17, *Nostoc linckia* 44, *Spirulina platensis* were isolated from various soils and water bodies of Uzbekistan (Fig. 1) [13-15]. In these studies, the

effects of light intensity and temperature on the growth and development of local strains of microalgae, particularly on biomass production, were investigated.

It is known that the biotechnological production and cultivation of microalgae in artificial conditions and in order to reduce production costs are carried out in nutrient media containing mineral salts using light sources, in these processes it is necessary to optimize nutrients and photosynthetically active light and temperature sources. According to the data presented in Table 1, the unicellular algae *C. vulgaris* 4 and *S. quadricauda* strains were found to accumulate optimal biomass at a light intensity of 3000 lux. In this case, the cultures produced 76.3% and 77.5% more dry biomass compared to *C. vulgaris* 4 and *S. quadricauda* 2000 lux, respectively. The studied cyanobacteria strains *Nostoc linckia* 44, *Anabaena variabilis* 17 and *Spirulina platensis* were observed to produce the highest amount of dry biomass at the light intensity level of 2500 lux. Specifically, *Anabaena variabilis* 17 cultures accumulated 79.8% more biomass at 2500 lux light intensity than at 2000 lux light intensity (Table 1). It is known that light intensity is an important parameter in the cultivation of cyanobacteria. High light intensity contributes significantly to values such as maximum growth rate, while lower light intensity results in the production of biomass richer in pigments and proteins [20,21].

Table 1

Effect of light intensity on growth and development (biomass) of microalgae

Cultures	Light intensity, lux				
	1000	2000	2500	3000	4000
	Biomass (dry weight), g/l				
<i>C. vulgaris</i> 4	0,572±0,02	0,645±0,02	0,718±0,02	0,845±0,1	0,812±0,01
<i>S. quadricauda</i>	0,544±0,01	0,639±0,03	0,748±0,1	0,824±0,02	0,794±0,02
<i>A. variabilis</i> 17	0,502±0,02	0,592±0,1	0,742±0,03	0,706±0,01	0,642±0,02
<i>N. linckia</i> 44	0,448±0,02	0,584±0,02	0,712±0,01	0,694±0,03	0,635±0,1
<i>S. platensis</i>	0,566±0,01	0,616±0,1	0,789±0,02	0,754±0,01	0,734±0,03

At the next stage, the effect of temperature on the growth and development of microalgae was studied. It is known that the average temperature in the Republic of Uzbekistan is 20-26 °C in spring, and 36-40 °C in summer.

Table 2

Effect of temperature on growth and development (biomass) of microalgae

Cultures	Temperature, °C				
	24	28	30	32	36
	Biomass (dry weight), g/l				
<i>C. vulgaris</i> 4	0,582±0,02	0,675±0,02	0,792±0,01	0,748±0,02	0,624±0,01
<i>S. quadricauda</i>	0,594±0,02	0,686±0,02	0,821±0,01	0,816±0,02	0,792±0,01
<i>A. variabilis</i> 17	0,588±0,01	0,728±0,1	0,708±0,02	0,696±0,1	0,614±0,02
<i>N. linckia</i> 44	0,584±0,02	0,694±0,02	0,676±0,02	0,672±0,01	0,634±0,1
<i>S. platensis</i>	0,596±0,1	0,734±0,02	0,724±0,01	0,712±0,02	0,694±0,02

Based on these data, cultures were grown at temperatures ranging from 24°C to 36°C to optimize microalgae growth conditions. It should be noted that biomass production of

cyanobacteria was observed to be maximum at 28°C. In particular, *S. platensis* culture accumulated the maximum biomass (0.734 g/l) at 28°C, which showed a decrease of 5.4% at 36°C (Table 2).

The obtained data show that the growth rate of unicellular green algae *C. vulgaris 4* and *S. quadricauda* at 30°C was higher than at 24°C and 36°C.

Conclusion

By changing different growth parameters of microalgae on an industrial scale, different target substances can be obtained (for example, pigments, carotenoids, fatty acids, peak biomass, etc.). The optimal temperature indicator for growing microalgae, light intensity depends on the characteristics of the strain. For example, the optimal temperature for *A. variabilis 17* was found to be 28°C, and for *C. vulgaris 4* strain it was 30°C. Thus, it is of particular interest to optimize cultivation conditions to obtain biomass of microalgae that synthesize biologically valuable substances. The growth and development of microalgae, as well as the accumulation of biomass, significantly depend on temperature, light intensity and other parameters (concentration of mineral substances in the nutrient medium, pH, aeration).

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